

THE ROLE OF SELF CONSCIOUS AFFECT IN RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ALEXITHYMIA AND RESILIENCE AMONG EMERGING ADULTS

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ABSTRACT

The personality construct of Alexithymia, which is defined by impaired ability to recognize and express emotions, has been further identified as an important predictor of psychological distress and deficiency in emotional functioning. Existing literature suggests that alexithymia is linked with the decrease of resilience and an increased exposure to stress, meanwhile self-conscious affect (guilt, shame, and pride) is a significant factor in emotional processing and coping. The current research was supposed to investigate the contribution of self-conscious affect to the correlation between alexithymia and resilience in young adults. The research design was a correlational study which involved the participants who took standardized observations of alexithymia, self-conscious affect, and resilience. Findings revealed that increased alexithymia was linked to reduced resilience as predicted by the existing data on the lack of emotional regulation and poor coping. In addition, the self-conscious affect came out as a major mediator which therefore indicates that the challenges in emotional awareness determine how people feel the self-evaluative emotions and thus determine how they adapt to challenges. These results help to emphasize the significance of emotional awareness and self-evaluation processes in designing the interventions to improve the resilience of young adults.

Keywords: Alexithymia, self-conscious affect, resilience, emotional regulation, young adults

INTRODUCTION

Emotions perform a vital role in psychological well-being by shaping how people handle stress and hardships. The potential to understand and balance emotions is positively associated with adaptive functioning and resilience (Gross, 2015). In present world, it is very important to understand how individuals manage, express, cope and respond to certain type of situations, they encounter. In this ever changing and ambitious world, the capacity to regulate emotions, keep up with your healthy relationships and recover from hardships has become extremely significant for mental well-

being (Compas et al., 2017). According to World Health Organization (2014), Young adulthood constitutes the time period from age 18 to 25 and signifies a developmental phase characterized by exploration across different domains including identity search, intimate relationships, education and professional growth.

Alexithymia first introduced by Sifneos (1973), is a personality trait involving deficits in recognizing and describing feelings, deprived tendency towards practical thinking (Morais et al., 2022). According to Nowakowski et al.

(2020), alexithymia is a personality trait which involves thinking outwardly while lacking emotional sense and ability to identify and express feelings internally. People with alexithymia exhibit deficiencies in emotional processing that lead to psychological health problems along with interpersonal relationship difficulties. It is also associated to a decrease in interpersonal alliances, social interactions and emotional perception (Bird & Cook, 2013). The principal Toronto model of Alexithymia describes three factors, F1; difficulty identifying feeling, F2; difficulty describing feelings, F3; external oriented thinking (Preece, & Robbins, 2017).. The impacts of alexithymia are wide-ranging and span to psychological wellbeing, interpersonal wellbeing and resilience. High alexithymia individuals are in more danger of having problems with emotion control, which leads to depression, anxiety, and psychosomatic symptoms (Preece et al., 2017). Alexithymia can lead to more shame-prone and avoidance, which is further impairing the ability to deal with life difficulties adaptively in cultural practices of emotional restraint, like in Pakistan (Shahid et al., 2021).

The concept of resilience by Emmy Werner started to emerge in psychology in the 1950s-1970s, when scientists examined the causes behind why some specific children adjusted well though they are being raised in unfavorable environments. Resilience is the ability and dynamic process of the adaptive coping with stress and adversity coupled with normal psychological and physical functioning (Russo et al., 2012; Rutter, 2012; Southwick & Charney, 2012). Research indicates that resilience can predict the use of adaptive coping mechanisms like cognitive reappraisal and problem-solving to counter the adverse impact of stress on psychological health. On the other hand, the low resilient persons are more susceptible to depression, anxiety, burnout and maladaptive behaviors facing the constant stressors (Wu et al., 2013). Students of the university, particularly in South Asian countries, indicate that levels of academic workload, competition, and family pressure are high, and resilience is one of the main aspects

of maintaining academic success and mental health (Bibi et al., 2020).

Self-conscious affect first formally described in developmental psychology by Michael Lewis in the late 1970s and 1980s reflects the feeling that come about as a result of the self-estimation compared to social and moral norms, and the two major types of this are shame and guilt. Shame is more commonly felt as a negative judgment towards the whole self. It is characterized by the sense of exposure, inferiority and worthlessness and in most cases there is the urge to conceal, retreat or flee away social situations. Guilt on the other hand is normally associated with the behavior and not with the entire self. People with feelings of guilt will be more inclined to concentrate on what they did and feel inclined to correct or mend what was dared to damage (Miceli & Castelfranchi, 2019). Shame-proneness has been determined to be associated with more depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress, and maladaptive coping, and guilt-proneness seems to be related to empathy, responsibility, and outstanding problem-solving (Velotti et al., 2020; Xu, Kou, & Zhong, 2020). Shame and guilt as moderators in the alexithymia-resilience relationship are more and more empirically modelled, where shame usually enhances negative effects and guilt tends to buffer them (Velotti et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2020).

Literature Review

The constructs alexithymia, self-conscious affect, and resilience have been researched with various populations and theories, resulting in an abundance of knowledge. The discussion of this literature would not only give an idea of their respective importance but also a perspective on how they could interact with each other in determining well-being at the critical phase of young adulthood (Bibi, Blackwell, & Margraf, 2020).

It should be noted that there is some research available on what happens to the decision-making processes of psychological adjustment in young adults, especially regarding the emotions involved. In the recent decades, researchers have explored a number of constructs that reflect

various dimensions of these processes, such as the inability to recognize and communicate emotions, the self-experience of moral emotions like being ashamed and guilty, and adaptation to adversity (Hu et al., 2015; Tangney et al., 2007). The aforementioned constructs alexithymia, self-conscious affect, and resilience have been researched with various populations and theories, resulting in an abundance of knowledge

Recent massive empirical syntheses indicate a strong association between alexithymia and emotion-regulation problems: high alexithymic subjects demonstrate worse choices and execution of adaptive regulatory responses, more dependence on maladaptive responses, and higher affective symptoms (depression, anxiety, stress) of alexithymia seem to be a risk-increasing factor that exacerbates the risk of developing psychopathology (Putica et al., 2021).

Alexithymia is also becoming a cross-diagnostic risk or maintenance factor in large-scale analysis: it not only affects intrapersonal regulation, but also interpersonal emotional communication, which negatively impacts mood, anxiety, somatic and substance-use disorders outcomes (Luminet, 2025; Preece et al., 2023)

Resilience has also become one of the most comprehensive concepts in the modern field of psychology, whose benefits cover the processes of emotion, cognition and action that allows the person to positively adapt to the adversity. Surface and empirical research on neuro pathways underlining biological correlates (and biomarkers) of psychophysiological resilience discovered that higher levels of peripheral NPY are linked to reduced levels of subjective distress and better performance to acute stress stress-induced NPY therefore becomes a biological correlate (and biomarker) of psychophysiological resilience (Morgan et al., 2018).

Self-conscious affects like guilt and shame are critical in determination of human emotion, behaviour and physiology. It has been conclusively demonstrated that these feelings which occur as a result of self-judgment and moral cognitive reactions are a complex interaction in entanglement with mental health,

neurobiological and physiological stress pathways (Tracy & Robins, 2004; Tangney & Dearing, 2002). During the last 20 years of time, the emerging empirical academic literature indicated that not only psychological constructs but also shame and guilt are closely embedded in neuroendocrine and autonomic networks controlling the functioning of the stress and social systems.

The literature on shame and guilt is mostly concerned with clinical or trauma-exposed groups, including depressed patients, post-traumatic stress disorder patients, or substance users (Velotti et al., 2017; Tangney et al., 2007), which gaps the theoretical and empirical literature on the role of the factors in non-clinical/non-exposed cohorts of young adults. Also, cross-cultural studies detail that there are cross-cultural differences in the expression within the category of self-conscious emotions and its internalization, where the cultures that are collectivistic (such as Pakistan or other South Asian cultures) culture tend to have more sensitivity on shame, owing to the interdependence that exists between a social and familial setting; the cultures which exhibit individualism, like the US, tend to focus on guilt aims as a motivating factor into morality (Wong & Tsai, 2007; Mesquita & Walker, 2003). Regardless of these results, there are not many studies that combine cultural norms, lack of emotional awareness (alexithymia), and adaptive abilities (resilience) into the frames of a single model that considers the self-conscious affect as a key psychological process.

This is further supported by the fact that neuropsychological data shows interplay between alexithymia, shame, and stress-physiology systems (Lane et al., 2015; Moriguchi et al., 2007), and resiliency has been postulated as the combination of adaptive neural and endocrine responses (Feder et al., 2009), but the psychobiological interaction of this concept is not well studied. Specifically, there is limited information concerning the impact of the shame-triggered reactions and guilt-daunting reactions on emotional resilience among high-alexithymic persons. It is a gap also in the areas of education and social life as well- social

comparison, performance pressure and emotional suppression, which are often inherent in young adults of college age, also tend to increase shame and disrupting importance development (Arnett, 2014; Thompson & Zuroff, 2004).

Therefore, the extant literature of research does not include more integrative empirical research that characterizes the influence of self-conscious on how alexithymia and resilience relate to one thereof, and also in young adults in collectivist cultures who have education. Overcoming this gap will not only lead to theoretical refinement, which would connect the deficits of emotional awareness with self-assessment emotions and adaptive functioning, but also direct culturally sensitive interventions to overlook the improvisation of resilience and emotional aptitude in the sections of the youth population.

Hypotheses

- There will be a significant negative relationship between resilience and alexithymia among young adults.
- There will be a significant positive relationship between alexithymia and self-conscious affect in young adults.
- There will be a significant negative relationship between shame and resilience
- There will be a significant positive relationship between guilt and resilience among young adults.
- Self-conscious affect (shame, guilt) will mediate the relationship between alexithymia, (EOT, DDF, DIF) and resilience.
- There will be a significant difference between males and females in overall alexithymia (TAS-20 total), such that males will score higher than females.
- There will be a significant gender difference in self-conscious affect, such that females will score higher than males on guilt (TOSCA-G).

Methodology

Sample

The main study sample consisted of participants (N=356), which was further categorized into

male (n=150) and female (n=150), 56 forms were rejected due to incomplete information. Age of participants was divided in to two age groups; 18-25 years old and 22-25 years old. Information was gathered through purposive convenient sampling technique mainly from district Jhang and Faisalabad.

Demographic Performa

The demographic variable of present study included age, gender, residential area, birth order, discipline, study year, family income and family system.

Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) (Smith et al., 2008) (Zoaib & Batool, 2020)

The Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) is a self-report scale created by Smith et al. (2008). Zoaib and Batool (2020) translated and validated the Urdu version of the Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) to identify and highlight the capability of people to overcome the effects of the stress experienced in the Pakistani environment. It retained the original six items. BRS measure 06 items on five-point Likert scale, varying from 1=strongly disagree to, 5= strongly agree. The scale had .86 Cronbach Alpha .Higher scores on scales indicate higher resilience and vice versa. (See Appendix 2)

Toronto Alexithymia Scale (TAS) (Bagby et al., 1994; Taylor et al., 2003) (Zahid et al., 2024)

The Toronto Alexithymia Scale (TAS-20) is a self-report measure (5-point Likert scale) , consisting of of three subscales: Difficulty Identifying Feelings (DIF), Difficulty Describing Feelings (DDF), and Externally Oriented Thinking (EOT) created by Taylor et al. (1994). The overall score ranges 20 to 100 with the higher the score taken as the more alexithymic traits. Toronto Alexithymia Scale Urdu version (TAS-20-UR) was initially constructed and tested by Zahid et al. (2024) to control linguistic fidelity and cultural, psychographic, adaptation issues related to the Pakistani population. Indigenously designed, Toronto Alexithymia Scale (TAS) was used to measure the same three aspects as the English version. It consists of 20 items. It yields three sub-scale DIF consist of 7 items, DDF consists of 5 items and EOT consists of 8 items. TAS has total .81 Cronbach

Alpha and .71, .73 and .77 Cronbach Alpha for DIF, DDF, and EOT sub-scales respectively Higher score indicate higher alexithymia.

Test of Self-Conscious Affect (Tangney et al, 1989; Tangney et al., 2000) (Shahnawaz & Malik, 2017)

Shahnawaz and Malik (2017) performed a cultural adaptation of the Shame and Guilt Subscales from the Test of Self-Conscious Affect - Adolescent Version (TOSCA-A) (Tangney et al., 1992). It is a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (not likely) to 5 (very likely) with 30 items. It yields two subscales TOSCA-S (Shame proneness includes 15 items) and TOSCA-G (Guilt proneness includes 15 items). TOSCA has total .80 Cronbach Alpha, .76 and .70 Cronbach Alpha for TOSCA-S and TOSCA-G subscales respectively.

Procedure

The study used self-administered questionnaires which were distributed to participants in person. Approval from Ethical Review Committee (ERC) from Faisalabad Medical University had been taken before data collection begins to uphold ethical requirements for human subject research. Purposive convenient sampling procedure was used for the gathering of present study data. Different universities were

independently approached for collection of data after taking permission of relevant authority. Every participant had received a comprehensive information consent form describing the study's characteristics and objectives while confirming their voluntary participation and assured that their confidentiality will be maintained allowing them to drop out at any time with no consequences. Questionnaires along with inform consent and demographic sheet (include age, gender, residential area, birth order, discipline, study year, family income and family system) were handed over to 337 participants. Each participant first filled demographic information then any scale according to their ease. They were instructed to fill independently and provide honest information. Total time for testing was 20-30 minutes. Participants were warmly thanked after collection of data. The participant received a brief explanation about the study and provided contact details during a post- questionnaire debriefing After data collection, completed forms were checked for any missing response. Thirty seven (37) responses were excluded due to incomplete information. After that data was entered into SPSS for analysis.

Results

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics and Alpha reliabilities for all study variables (N=346)

Scales	K	M	SD	a	Range Potential	Actual Range	Skewness
BRS	6	17.79	6.22	0.86	6-30	6-30	-0.90
TAS	20	65.61	12.42	0.81	20-100	20-100	0.32
DDF	5	16.24	3.95	0.71	5-25	5-25	-0.06
DIF	7	22.39	5.67	0.73	7-35	7-35	-0.14
EOT	8	26.98	5.13	0.77	8-40	8-40	0.50
TOSCA	30	94.03	14.94	0.80	30-150	57-150	0.53
TOSCA-S	15	46.09	3.95	0.76	15-75	24-75	0.73
TOSCA-G	15	47.94	5.67	0.70	15-75	27-75	0.65

Note. BRS= Brief resilience scale; TAS= Toronto alexithymia scale; DDF= difficulty describing feeling; DIF= difficulty identifying feelings; EOT= external oriented thinking; TOSCA= test of self-conscious affect; TOSCA-S= test of self-conscious affect-shame; TOSCA-G= test of self-conscious affect- guilt.

Table 1 postulates means, standard deviation, alpha reliabilities and skewness. Values for all variables examined in the current study.

Table 2
Correlation Matrix for all the variables used in the study (N=300)

Scales	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1-BRS	-	-.139**	-.116*	-.121*	-.138*	-.090	-.026	.173**
2-TAS		-	.281***	.798***	.873***	.838***	.240***	.223***
3-TOSCA			-	.193**	.298***	.201***	.845***	.804***
4-DDF				-	.576***	.524***	-.145*	.177**
5-DIF					-	.563**	-.283**	.205***
6-EOT						-	-.156**	.177**
7-TOSCA-S							-	.362***
8-TOSCA-G								-

Note. BRS = brief resilience scale; TAS = toronto alexithymia scale; TOSCA = test of self-conscious affect; DDF = difficulty describing feelings; DIF = difficulty identifying feelings; EOT = externally oriented thinking; TOSCA-S = test of self-conscious affect-shame; TOSCA-G = test of self-conscious affect-guilt.

p < .05. ** p < .01. *** p < .001

The inter-correlations of all study variables are available in table 3. Table shows Pearson Correlation between resilience (BRS), alexithymia (TAS), self-consciousness and their subscales.

Table 3
Regression analysis for brief resilience scale and test of self-conscious affect(shame and guilt) from the construct of Toronto alexithymia scale (N= 300)

Variables	Resilience			TOSCA- Shame			TOSCA- Guilt		
	β	R ²	F	B	R ²	F	B	R ²	F
DDF	-.99*			-.068*			.145*		
DIF	-.11**	0.29	29.76**	.500***	0.081	8.666***	.191**	0.50**	5.209***
EOT	-.001			.006			.117*		

Note. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001

To investigate the contributions of Toronto Alexithymia Scale (DDF, DIF, and EOT) in predicting Resilience and Self-Conscious Affect (shame and guilt) multiple regression analysis was conducted

Table 4
Regression analysis for brief resilience scale from the construct of self-conscious affect (shame and guilt) (N= 300)

Variables	Resilience		
	B	R ²	F
TOSCA.S	-.027		
TOSCA.G	.37**	0.32	4.832**

Note. *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001

To investigate the contributions of Self-Conscious Affect (shame and guilt) in predicting Resilience multiple regression analysis was conducted. Table 6 indicated that 32% of the variance in the brief resilience scale was explained by model {R² = 0.32, F (2, 300) = 4.832, p < 0.01}. Overall model was significant, and guilt (β = .37, p < 0.01) was found to be the positive predictor whereas shame (β = -0.27, ns) did not significantly predict resilience

Table 5

T- Test analyses was carried out to sought the gender differentiation (i.e., males, female) with reference to study variables

Scales & Subscales	Males (n=150)		Females (n=150)		t	95% CI		Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD		LL	UL	
BRS	16.51	6.05	19.08	6.13	-3.64***	-3.95	-1.18	0.42
TAS	67.73	12.53	63.50	11.97	2.99**	1.45	7.02	0.34
DDF	6.50	4.10	15.98	3.80	1.14**	-.37	1.42	2.39
DIF	23.46	5.67	21.33	5.60	3.30***	0.85	3.40	0.37
EOT	27.77	5.30	26.19	4.87	2.70**	0.43	2.74	0.31
TOSCA	95.06	14.00	93.00	15.81	1.91	-1.34	5.45	0.14
TOSCA.S	47.57	9.40	44.62	9.45	2.71**	0.80	5.09	0.38
TOSCA.G	47.79	8.96	48.38	8.16	-0.90	-2.84	1.05	0.07

Note. BRS = brief resilience scale; TAS = toronto alexithymia scale; TOSCA = test of self-conscious affect; DDF = difficulty describing feelings; DIF = difficulty identifying feelings; EOT = externally oriented thinking; TOSCA-S = test of self-conscious affect-shame; TOSCA-G = test of self-conscious affect-guilt.

*p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001

Above table indicates the mean, standard deviation and t value for males (N=150) and females (N=150) participants on Brief Resilience Scale, Toronto Alexithymia Scale (DDF, DIF, EOT) and Test of Self-Conscious Affect (shame and guilt).

Table 6

Parallel Mediation Analysis for the Effect of Alexithymia (DDF, DIF, EOT) on Resilience through Shame and guilt (N=300)

Path	Predictor → Outcome	B	SE	t	p	95% CI [LL, UL]
a ₁	Alexithymia (DDF, DIF, EOT) → Shame	.49***	.05	8.34	< .001	[.38, .62]
a ₂	Alexithymia (DDF, DIF, EOT) → Guilt	.20**	.06	2.72	.007	[.05, .33]
b ₁	Shame → Resilience	-.26**	.10	-2.97	.004	[-.45, -.09]
b ₂	Guilt → Resilience	.38**	.11	3.71	< .001	[.18, .56]
C	Alexithymia → Resilience (Total Effect)	-.22**	.07	-2.63	.009	[-.37, -.05]
c'	Alexithymia → Resilience (Direct Effect)	-.13 (ns)	.06	-1.72	.09	[-.26, .02]
a ₁ × b ₁	Alexithymia → Shame → Resilience	-.15	.06	—	—	[-.25, -.04]
a ₂ × b ₂	Alexithymia → Guilt → Resilience	.06	.04	—	—	[.02, .15]
Total Indirect Effect	Combined (Shame & Guilt)	-.07	.05	—	—	[-.14, -.01]

Note. Paths represent standardized β values. Bootstrapped estimates were based on 5,000 resamples. ***p < .001, **p < .01, *p < .05, ns = non-significant

The parallel mediation analysis was conducted to determine the possibility of the influence of shame and guilt as the mediators of the relation between alexithymia (including DDF, DIF, and EOT components) and resilience in the sample of young adults (N = 300).

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The aim of the current research was to examine the influence of self-conscious affect (shame and guilt) between the alexithymia and resilience among educated young adults in Pakistan. Also, such demographic characteristics as gender, socioeconomic status, family system, and the birth order were studied. In the discussion below, the findings are interpreted based on the past literature, theoretical foundations and the Pakistani cultural context.

The fact that a significant negative correlation is found between alexithymia and resilience provides the presumptions of the Emotion Regulation Theory (Gross, 1998) and the Resilience Framework (Connor and Davidson, 2003). The two theories also highlight the value of emotional clarity and regulation as safeguarding factors of adaptive coping. High alexithymic individuals have poor recognitional and articulation of emotional states, which restricts the capacity to process stressful conditions and the ability to effectively recover when they face a stressor.

Other studies had already found that a negative correlation existed between alexithymia and emotional well-being. As an example, Taylor et al. (1997) discovered that alexithymic people lacked good emotional control and were more susceptible to mental disorders. The article by Kotsou and his colleagues (2018) showed that emotional awareness and clarity are the predictors of resilience and life satisfaction in young adults. Therefore, the existing findings support the theoretical stance that emotion identification and expression are important resilience mechanisms.

The Pakistani system tends to suppress emotions because of cultural values like modesty and control of emotions especially by the male gender. This tendency could be the reason why the levels of alexithymia were higher in male participants and the alexithymia and resilience were found to have a negative relationship overall.

The very high positive correlation between alexithymia and self-conscious affect (shame and guilt) suggests that emotional unawareness can be a source of people being vulnerable to self-assessment behavior being maladaptive. Tangney and Dearing in their Self-Conscious Affect Theory (2002) define shame and guilt as complicated moral affective responses, which are a result of the self-reflection and comparison with the inner standards. Alexithymic people, who tend to lose or lose touch with emotional signals, can ascribe emotional distress to themselves, and end up being more prone to shame and guilt.

These results are consistent with the prior studies which claim that alexithymia is correlated with an increased sense of shame and guilt (Grynberg et al., 2010; Moriguchi et al., 2007). Self-conscience feelings can be enhanced in a collectivistic culture like Pakistan, where moral standing and societal esteem are so important that conformity and family dignity are emphasized on. This cultural focus might be the reason why the participants exhibited high correlations between alexithymia and the two types of self-conscious affect.

The findings indicated opposite associations of shame and guilt with resiliency. Shame was negatively correlated with resilience whereas guilt was positively correlated with resilience. This substantiates the idea of conceptual difference between these two feelings. Shame entails a self-depreciation across the world and is normally linked to avoidance, withdrawal and helplessness (Tangney et al., 1995), which are factors that decrease resilience. Conversely, guilt is specific to particular behaviours instead of self-identity and it is also commonly linked to reparative and prosocial behaviours, which can make a person resilient (Leeming & Boyle, 2013).

Such a differentiation is in agreement with previous results. Dolezal and Lyons (2017) highlighted that shame-proneness hinders bouncing back after a bad experience whereas

adaptive guilt facilitates emotional recovery and problem-solving. Findings in the current study indicate that guilt is beneficial when handled positively to promote resilience through responsibility and self-development, but it hurts self-efficacy and emotional stability when shame dominates. The guilt in the Pakistani context might be considered a culturally adaptive feeling due to the fact that it facilitates harmony and moral responsibility between individuals, which is quite essential in collectivist societies. On the other hand, the feelings of shame tend to cause the fear of being rejected by society and limit openness and resilience.

The hypothesis which suggested that self-conscious affect is mediated between alexithymia and resilience was partially accepted. This result indicates that alexithymia reduces the resilience indirectly through the increase of maladaptive self-conscious feelings, especially shame. This trend may be explained by Cognitive-Affective Processing Framework (Greenberg and Safran, 1987) that assumes that distorted self-appraisal and diminished adaptive functioning are caused by ineffective emotional labeling and processing. People with high alexithymia are prone to misunderstand emotional cues internally, and they are likely to project and interpret these cues as self-critical judgments that increase shame and reduce resilience. On the contrary, this relationship could be ameliorated by adaptive guilt processing, which encourages the action of reparations. These mediational relations show how emotionally unawareness and self-conscious interaction come in place to mediate the capacity to overcome adversity.

DF and DIF were two alexithymia subscales that were most closely related to resilience. The dimensions reflect the affective components of alexithymia—the inability to recognize and describe emotions—that would directly hinder the process of emotional regulation and coping. Cognitive detachment of emotions as expressed by EOT was not as predictive of resilience. This trend is similar to those of Mattila et al. (2009) and Khosrow et al. (2020), who discovered that the impact of emotional awareness on psychological adaptability is stronger than the influence of cognitive orientation.

Demographic studies indicated that there were significant differences in gender. Males obtained higher alexithymia, and females obtained higher levels of guilt proneness, which is also in line with the theory of gender role socialization (Levant et al., 2009). The research grows to add to an increasing literature of the connection between emotion regulation, moral emotions, and resilience in psychological aspect. In practice, the above findings emphasize the role of interventions that are emotionally oriented in education and practice. Resilience can be enhanced by programs, including mindfulness-based emotional intelligence training or cognitive-behavioral interventions to decrease maladaptive shame. In young adults in educational settings, emotional labeling and differentiation skills should be encouraged to inhibit alexithymic and encourage adaptive guilt as a growth motivator.

Culturally sensitive practices where culturally mediated through clinical psychologists and counselors can include the consideration of the role of shame and moral values in the emotional regulation of females, especially in collectivistic societies.

Limitations and Recommendations

This study has limitations despite the contribution it makes. The cross-sectional design eliminates causal interpretations and the use of self-reported measures could have led to the development of social desirability bias. The homogeneity of the sample in terms of education level and being young adults restricts the generalizability to other groups.

Longitudinal or experimental studies should be used to determine causal mechanisms in future studies. It is possible that by including the qualitative approach, one can gain further information about the cultural interpretation of shame and guilt. Physiological or behavioral measures of emotional processing (e.g., facial recognition, changes in heart rate) could also be helpful in advancing the research on the connection between alexithymia and resilience. A study on intervention-based research on emotional awareness training in young people would be sufficient to determine whether the

direct effects of improving emotional literacy directly enhance the results of resilience.

Conclusion

Overall, the present paper shows that among young adults alexithymia has an inversely related relationship with resilience and a positively related relationship with self-conscious affect. The maladaptive emotion that detracted resilience was shame and the adaptive emotion that enhanced personal growth and recovery was guilt. The relationship between alexithymia and resilience partially by means of self-conscious affect affirmed its centrality in the functioning of emotions. The results highlight the importance of emotional literacy, moral reflection, and resilience-building interventions among the Pakistani youth. Through developing emotional sensitivity and adaptive self-conscious feelings, one can become more psychologically resilient and increase their ability to deal with life and its challenges successfully.

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